

Supplementary material – data extraction form

Post-discharge Care Interventions to Support Patient Recovery after Elective Degenerative Spine Surgery – a systematic review

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This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1).

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	12-08-2022		
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL		
Author(s)	Aldemir, K et al.		
Country	Türkiye		
Publication year	2021		
Title of article	The effect of pedometer-supported walking and telemonitoring after disc hernia surgery on pain and disability levels and quality of life		
Title of journal	International Journal of Nursing Practice (John Wiley & Sons, Inc.)		
Volume 27	Issue 2	Pages 1-12	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Research article		

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1, 2
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	The personal characteristics of the patients (N = 67) Intervention 33, control 34				p. 6, 7
	The mean age of the participants in the intervention group was 42.30 (SD = 9.92) (range, 29–65), whereas the mean age of the participants in the control group was	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

	44.88 (SD = 9.25) (range, 31–64) Disc hernia surgery Standard lumbar discectomy using a microsurgical technique				p. 1 p. 2
Types of intervention	Pedometer-supported walking and telemonitoring	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1, 4
Types of comparison	No walking exercise	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1 (abstract)
Types of outcome measures	Pain, disability, quality of life, activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3-4, 7 (table 2, fig. 2), 8 (table 3), 9 (table 4 and 5)
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of pedometer-supported walking and telemonitoring on patients' pain, disability and quality of life after LDH surgery	p. 2
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	This was a randomized controlled trial with two randomly selected groups This experimental study randomly assigned patients to intervention and control groups.	p. 1 (abstract) p. 2
Unit of allocation (by individuals, cluster/groups or body parts)	Allocated to receive and not to receive walking exercise	p. 1 (abstract)
Start date	March 2018	p. 1 (abstract)
End date	January 2019	p. 1 (abstract)

Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	<p>Before the study, ethical board permission from Marmara University School of Medicine Clinical Research Board of Ethics was taken (date: 3 October 2017, protocol number: 09.2017.648). Additionally, institutional permission from the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Health Services Application and Research Hospital Chief Physician's Office was taken (6 November 2017, number 93596471-000).</p>	p. 5
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Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	The Neurosurgery Clinic of the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Health Services Application and Research Hospital	p. 2
Inclusion criteria	Patients who were scheduled for standard lumbar discectomy using a microsurgical technique, with no vision or hearing deficits (unless they were compensated using visual and auditory aid tools), not having speech impairment or communication problems, not having mental health problems, being literate and owning a cellular phone.	p. 2
Exclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria were being of 70 years of age and above, not being able to speak, read or write in Turkish, having physical and cognitive problems to the level of not being able to use a cell phone, receiving repeating LDH surgeries and having joint, ligament or vascular diseases (such as intermittent claudication) to the point of not being able to walk.	p. 2
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	<p>Informed consent was obtained from all participants. The principles of the Helsinki Declaration were upheld throughout the study.</p>

Intervention groups

Intervention Group 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Intervention group	p. 6, table 1
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=33 (F16 / M17)	p. 6, table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	The program formed for sedentary individuals by the American College of Sports Medicine (2009) was used in this study. This program starts with a minimum of 10 min (approximately 1200 steps) of walking 4 days a week and continues with a minimum of 30 min of moderate intensity walking for a minimum of 5 days a week (American College of Sports Medicine, 2009). Because an important improvement on the level of physical activity of patients in the first 3 months after LDH surgery has been reported (Mobbs et al., 2016), the walking program was applied for 3 months in the current study.	p. 4

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group	p. 6, table 1
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=34 (F18 / M16)	p. 6, table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Control group treatment: Face-to-face interviews performed on the day before surgery, three weeks after surgery, and in the first-, second-, and third-month follow-ups. No walking exercise.	p. 4,5

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain	p. 3, 5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	The Short Form McGill Pain Questionnaire Favors intervention	p. 3, 5 Table 2

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Disability	p. 4, 7
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	The Modified Oswestry Disability Index Favors intervention	4, 7 Table 2+3

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Quality of life	p. 4, 8
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	36-Item Short Form Survey Favors intervention	p. 4, 8 Table 5

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Daily physical activity	p. 4, p. 7 (fig. 2)
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Number of steps, walking duration (min.) and walking distance (km)	p. 8 (table 3)

Follow-up

Follow-up	3 months	p. 7-9
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>The pedometer-supported walking and telemonitoring intervention in the early post-operative period increased the physical activity levels of the patients, decreased their pain and disability levels and increased their quality of life after LDH surgery. In this context, nurses can train patients on free walking to gradually increase their physical activity levels during discharge training. Especially because patients with low physical activity levels before surgery also have low physical activity after surgery, they may need extra support in reaching the desired physical activity levels, and nurses can support patients through telemonitoring. Additionally, hospital managements can increase the use of technological observation methods in nursing activities after discharge. Thus, cost-effective care can be provided by decreasing repeated hospitalizations. Because such applications would contribute more to the general health levels of patients, they would also contribute to the improvement of nursing care quality.</p> <p>Results: Compared with the control group, pain level at the first and second months and disability level at the second and third months in the intervention group were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$), and in the third month, subdimension scores of quality of life (the physical role difficulty, energy and vitality, mental health, social functionality and pain) were higher ($p < 0.05$).</p>	<p>p. 10</p> <p>Figure 1 p. 1, abstract</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>